

A Breakthrough in Die Bonding Technique on Thin Semiconductor Die

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I. OVERVIEW

- Die attach or die bonding process is one of the key processes in integrated circuit (IC) assembly, responsible in the “picking and bonding” of semiconductor die from the wafer to a carrier
- A rubber pick-up and non-conductive needle material incorporated in a pneumatic-controlled assembly in Fig. 1 enables the separation of the semiconductor die from the wafer

Fig. 1. Pick-up process for standard silicon die.

II. PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION

- The continuous demand for densification and miniaturization of semiconductor product sets new standard in diebonding technology
- As the thickness of silicon die shifts to thinner requirement and applications, the pick and place process becomes a critical part of the IC assembly
- Thinner silicon die is more susceptible to the stress induced by the assembly process in Fig. 2 resulting to semiconductor die anomalies or defects

Fig. 2. Illustration of potential factors during pick-up sequence contributing to silicon die defects.

III. PROCESS DESIGN SOLUTION AND IMPROVEMENT

- A modification and improvement in the standard pick and place process is presented in Fig. 3 through understanding and proper identification of factors that contribute to a certain defect

Fig. 3. Modified pick-up process.

- The augmented and improved machine pick and place sequence eliminates the direct collision of the assembly on the silicon die